

Yield response of transplanted aman rice as influenced by weed management practice under conservation agriculture system

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Losses in crop yield as a result of increased weed pressure are the major hurdles to the widespread adoption of conservation agriculture system (CA). However, the recent development of broad spectrum herbicides provides an opportunity to control weeds in CA (Sharma *et al.*, 2013). But options for weed control must reduce selection pressure for herbicide resistance interaction weeds (Hossain *et al.*, 2014). In CA systems the presence of residue on the soil surface may influence soil temperature and moisture regimes that affect weed seed germination and emergence patterns thus help in reducing weed. Crop yields can be similar for conventional and conservation tillage systems if weeds are controlled and crop stands are uniform (Mahajan *et al.*, 2002). Considering the above facts, an on-farm experiment was conducted, to examine the performance of tillage practices and residue levels on crop and weeds.

METHODOLOGY

The research on-farm was conducted at the Durbacakra village under Gouripur Upazila of Mymensingh district of Bangladesh during *Kharif II* season 2014. Hybrid rice cv. *Hybrid Krishan2*, was transplanted with six tillage and weed control practices viz., (i) Conventional tillage + farmer's weeding practice (Control); (ii) Roundup (RU) + Strip tillage (ST); (iii) RU + ST + Pre-emergence (PE) herbicide (Pendimethalin); (iv) RU + ST + Post-emergence (PO) herbicide (Ethoxysulfuron); (v) RU+ ST + PE + PO; (vi) RU+ ST + weed-free (WF), and two levels of crop residue viz., (R₂₀) 20% residue and (R₅₀) 50% residue. The treatments were laid out in randomized complete block design with four replications using unit plots of 9 m × 5 m. Weed species and plant densities were recorded randomly from 4 locations of 0.25 m² each. Weed dry matter assessed by harvesting biomass which was then oven dried at 70^o C for 72 hours. The crop was harvested at maturity and data were recorded. Data were subjected to ANOVA using MSTAT-C and means separated by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

RESULTS

Pre-emergence herbicide reduced the density by 41%, post-emergence reduced 43% and combination of both reduced 53% density compared to roundup alone while roundup alone reduced 11% compared to conventional practice. 50% residue reduced density by 35% compared to 20% residue. Pre-emergence or post-emergence herbicide reduced 28% biomass while the combination of both reduced 55% biomass compared to roundup alone. There was 16% on average biomass reduction in 50% residue compared to 20% residue (Table 1).

The highest grain (24% higher compared to control) yielded from strip tilled weed free treatment. Combination of pre-emergence and post-emergence herbicide yielded 13 % higher grain compared to conventional practice or roundup alone. Strip tillage with only pre-emergence and only post-emergence herbicide yielded the identical grain. The higher (50%) residue yielded 4% higher grains compared to 20% residue. The correlation between weed biomass and grain yield revealed that, the lower the biomass the higher the grain yield. The highest BCR was calculated from strip tillage sprayed both pre and post-emergence herbicide while the conventional practice earned the lowest. Retention of 50% residue yielded 11% higher grains.

Table 1. Treatments effect on weed and crop

Tillage and weed control practice	Residue level	Weed density (no./m ²)	Weed dry matter (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	B. C. ratio
CT	R ₂₀	40a	57.52a	5.17gh	1.63g
	R ₅₀	25b	50.28b	5.20g	1.76g
RU+ST	R ₂₀	28b	51.61b	5.18g	2.15f
	R ₅₀	20c	42.09c	5.27f	2.42e
RU+ST+PE	R ₂₀	16cd	40.02cd	5.41e	2.44e
	R ₅₀	14d	37.34de	5.52d	2.56de
RU+ST+PO	R ₂₀	13d	36.18de	5.43e	2.65d
	R ₅₀	8e	31.89e	5.56d	2.95c
RU+ST+PE+PO	R ₂₀	8e	27.69f	5.47c	3.49b
	R ₅₀	2f	14.25g	6.27b	4.17a
RU+ST+WF	R ₂₀	0f	0h	6.36b	3.10c
	R ₅₀	0f	0h	6.56a	3.30b
LSD (P=0.05)		4.41	4.73	0.032	0.18

CONCLUSION

Application of pre-emergence herbicide followed by post-emergence herbicide with the retention of higher level of crop residue could manage weeds satisfactorily which attribute the maximum outcome under CA practice.

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